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INVESTIGATING THE SUITABILITY OF *Paramecium sp.* AS A FIRST FEED FOR *Betta splendens* LARVAE

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Traditional feeding methods for rearing fish larvae have limitations in efficiency and cost-effectiveness. *Artemia*, the most common live feed, is expensive and requires specific hatching conditions, limiting its use by many farmers. As a result, egg yolk is often used as a cheaper alternative, though it provides lower nutritional value and growth. This study aimed to investigate the suitability of *Paramecium sp.* as a more efficient and cost-effective feed for fish larvae. Three days post fertilization (dpf), *Betta splendens* larvae were fed with 3 different diets, *Artemia sp.* (Control 1), egg yolk (Control 2), and *Paramecium sp.* (Treatment 1), 3 times a day for 10 days. Each treatment was triplicated. Initially, pH, temperature, Dissolved oxygen, ammonia, and nitrate were recorded to assess the influence of water quality parameters on larval fish survival and growth rates. Furthermore, the larval length and weight were measured using a ruler and an analytical balance, respectively. Final mean percentage survival rate \pm SE was 54.17 ± 3.63 (Control 1), 5.83 ± 0.83 (Control 2), and 7.50 ± 1.44 (Treatment 1). The mean final TL (mm) \pm SE was 6.29 ± 0.10 (*Artemia sp.*), 5.79 ± 0.21 (egg yolk), and 5.89 ± 0.20 (Treatment 1). The final mean weight (mg) \pm SE was 0.03 ± 0.00 (Control 1), 0.01 ± 0.00 (Control 2), and 0.01 ± 0.00 (Treatment 1). One-way ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the mean values of water quality parameters, final total length, and final weight among treatments. However, a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the final mean percentage survival rate of the *Betta splendens* larvae ($p < 0.05$). The present study demonstrated that *Paramecium sp.* could serve as a supplementary feeding option in low-cost larviculture systems of *Betta splendens*.

Keywords: *Betta splendens*, Growth performance, Larviculture, *Paramecium sp.*, Survival rate